

Solid Angles of a Tetrahedron and a Triangle from Face Angles and Vertex Position Vectors

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1. Introduction: This paper aims to find the solid angle subtended by any tetrahedron at its vertex, given the angles between the consecutive lateral edges meeting at that vertex, and the solid angle subtended by a triangular plane at the origin, given the vertex position vectors. In general, the solid angle subtended by any tetrahedron at its vertex is a function of angles between lateral edges meeting at that vertex.

2. Solid angle of a tetrahedron: Consider a tetrahedron OPQR such that α, β & γ are the angle between the consecutive lateral edges OP & OQ, OQ & OR, and OP & OR respectively meeting at the vertex O (as shown in Figure 1). Now, draw a spherical surface of radius R with centre at the vertex O of tetrahedron OPQR such that it intersects lateral edges OP, OQ, OR at the points A, B & C respectively (As shown in Figure 2 below). Join the points of intersection A, B & C by dotted straight lines & by great circle arcs to obtain a plane ΔABC & a spherical ΔABC . Now, we have (see Figure 2 below),

$$\text{In isosceles } \Delta AOB, \quad \Rightarrow AB = 2R \sin \frac{\alpha}{2}$$

$$\text{In isosceles } \Delta BOC, \quad \Rightarrow BC = 2R \sin \frac{\beta}{2}$$

$$\text{In isosceles } \Delta AOC, \quad \Rightarrow AC = 2R \sin \frac{\gamma}{2}$$

Now, applying cosine formula in plane ΔABC (Fig. 2),

$$\cos \angle C = \frac{(BC)^2 + (CA)^2 - (AB)^2}{2(BC)(CA)} = \frac{(2R \sin \frac{\beta}{2})^2 + (2R \sin \frac{\gamma}{2})^2 - (2R \sin \frac{\alpha}{2})^2}{2(2R \sin \frac{\beta}{2})(2R \sin \frac{\gamma}{2})}$$

$$\cos \angle C = \frac{\sin^2 \frac{\beta}{2} + \sin^2 \frac{\gamma}{2} - \sin^2 \frac{\alpha}{2}}{2 \sin \frac{\beta}{2} \sin \frac{\gamma}{2}}$$

The plane angle θ_p between the chords of any two great circle arcs meeting each other at an angle θ on a spherical surface are co-related by HCR's cosine formula [1] as follows

$$\cos \theta_p = \sin \frac{\delta}{2} \sin \frac{\varphi}{2} + \cos \frac{\delta}{2} \cos \frac{\varphi}{2} \cos \theta \quad \forall 0 < \delta, \varphi, \theta \leq \pi \Rightarrow 0 \leq \theta_p < \theta$$

$$\Rightarrow \cos \theta = \frac{\cos \theta_p - \sin \frac{\alpha}{2} \sin \frac{\beta}{2}}{\cos \frac{\alpha}{2} \cos \frac{\beta}{2}} \quad (\text{Rewriting for } \theta) \quad \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

where δ & φ are the angles subtended by two great circle arcs at the centre of the spherical surface.

Figure 1: α, β & γ are the angles between lateral edges OP, OQ & OR meeting at vertex O of tetrahedron OPQR.

Figure 2: Plane ΔABC & spherical ΔABC obtained by the intersection of spherical surface & lateral edges of tetrahedron OPQR, subtend equal solid angle at centre O of sphere.

Now, we have

θ_p = plane angle between chords (straight lines) BC & AC = $\angle C$ (see Fig. 2 above),

δ = angle subtended by great arc BC at the centre O = β ,

φ = angle subtended by great arc AC at the centre O = γ

Setting the corresponding values in the above Eq. (1), we get the angle θ_1 between the great circle arcs BC & AC (Fig. 2) as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
 \cos\theta_1 &= \frac{\cos\alpha C - \sin\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}}{\cos\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}} \\
 &= \frac{\frac{\sin^2\frac{\beta}{2} + \sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2} - \sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}{2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}} - \sin\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}}{\cos\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}} \\
 &= \frac{\sin^2\frac{\beta}{2} + \sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2} - \sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2} - 2\sin^2\frac{\beta}{2}\sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2}}{2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}} \\
 &= \frac{\left(\sin^2\frac{\beta}{2} - \sin^2\frac{\beta}{2}\sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2}\right) + \left(\sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2} - \sin^2\frac{\beta}{2}\sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2}\right) - \sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}{\frac{1}{2}\left(2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\beta}{2}\right)\left(2\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}\right)} \\
 &= \frac{\sin^2\frac{\beta}{2}\left(1 - \sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2}\right) + \sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2}\left(1 - \sin^2\frac{\beta}{2}\right) - \sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}{\frac{1}{2}(\sin\beta)(\sin\gamma)} \\
 &= \frac{2\left(\sin^2\frac{\beta}{2}\cos^2\frac{\gamma}{2} + \cos^2\frac{\beta}{2}\sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2} - \sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
 &= \frac{2\left(\sin^2\frac{\beta}{2}\cos^2\frac{\gamma}{2} + \cos^2\frac{\beta}{2}\sin^2\frac{\gamma}{2} + 2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}\cos\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2} - 2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}\cos\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2} - \sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
 &= \frac{2\left(\left(\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2} + \cos\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}\right)^2 - 2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}\cos\frac{\beta}{2}\sin\frac{\gamma}{2} - \sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
 &= \frac{2\left(\left(\sin\left(\frac{\beta+\gamma}{2}\right)\right)^2 - \frac{1}{2}\left(2\sin\frac{\beta}{2}\cos\frac{\beta}{2}\right)\left(2\sin\frac{\gamma}{2}\cos\frac{\gamma}{2}\right) - \sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
 &= \frac{2\left(\sin^2\left(\frac{\beta+\gamma}{2}\right) - \frac{1}{2}\sin\beta\sin\gamma - \sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}\right)}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
&= \frac{2\sin^2\left(\frac{\beta + \gamma}{2}\right) - \sin\beta\sin\gamma - 2\sin^2\frac{\alpha}{2}}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
&= \frac{(1 - \cos(\beta + \gamma)) - \sin\beta\sin\gamma - (1 - \cos\alpha)}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
&= \frac{\cos\alpha - \cos(\beta + \gamma) - \sin\beta\sin\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
&= \frac{\cos\alpha - (\cos\beta\cos\gamma - \sin\beta\sin\gamma) - \sin\beta\sin\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
&= \frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma + \sin\beta\sin\gamma - \sin\beta\sin\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
\cos\theta_1 &= \frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma} \\
\theta_1 &= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

Similarly, the angle θ_2 between the great circle arcs AC & AB can be found out as follows

$$\theta_2 = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\gamma\cos\alpha}{\sin\gamma\sin\alpha}\right)$$

Similarly, the angle θ_3 between the great circle arcs AB & BC can be found out as follows

$$\theta_3 = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right)$$

Thus, θ_1, θ_2 & θ_3 are the angles between great circle arcs AC & BC, AC & AB, and AB & BC, respectively (see Figure 2 above) which are also the interior angles of spherical triangle ABC.

Now, the solid angle subtended by the tetrahedron OPQR at its apex O (see Fig. 2 above) is given by the following formula based on the basic definitions [2,3] as follows

$$\begin{aligned}
\omega &= \text{solid angle subtended by spherical triangle ABC at the centre O of spherical surface of radius } R \\
&= \frac{\text{Area covered by spherical triangle ABC having interior angles } \theta_1, \theta_2 \text{ \& } \theta_3}{(\text{radius of spherical surface})^2} \\
&= \frac{(\theta_1 + \theta_2 + \theta_3 - \pi)R^2}{R^2} = \theta_1 + \theta_2 + \theta_3 - \pi \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right) + \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\gamma\cos\alpha}{\sin\gamma\sin\alpha}\right) + \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right) - \pi \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right) - \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\gamma\cos\alpha}{\sin\gamma\sin\alpha}\right)\right) - \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right)\right) \\
&= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\gamma\cos\alpha}{\sin\gamma\sin\alpha}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right)
\end{aligned}$$

Hence, the **solid angle subtended by any tetrahedron at its vertex** is given by the general formula

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\gamma\cos\alpha}{\sin\gamma\sin\alpha}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right) \dots (2)$$

Where, α, β & γ are the angles between consecutive lateral edges meeting at the concerned vertex of tetrahedron ($\forall 0 < \alpha, \beta, \gamma < \pi$ & $\alpha + \beta + \gamma < 2\pi$).

It is worth noticing that the above formula is valid in all the cases. It gives the maximum value of solid angle as 2π sr when the vertex of the tetrahedron lies on the plane of the base, which is true because the solid angle subtended by any plane at each point on it within its boundary is always 2π sr.

3. Solid angle subtended by any triangle at the origin in 3D co-ordinate system given the position

vectors of the vertices: Let's consider any triangle ABC in 3D space such that \vec{a}, \vec{b} & \vec{c} are the position vectors of the vertices A, B & C, respectively (as shown in Figure 3).

Now, let $\angle AOB = \alpha$, $\angle BOC = \beta$ & $\angle AOC = \gamma$ then we use vector product & scalar product of two vectors, the vector product \vec{a} & \vec{b} is given as

$$\vec{a} \times \vec{b} = |\vec{a}||\vec{b}|\sin\alpha\hat{n} \Rightarrow \sin\alpha = \frac{|\vec{a} \times \vec{b}|}{|\vec{a}||\vec{b}|}$$

The scalar product \vec{a} & \vec{b} is given as

$$\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b} = |\vec{a}||\vec{b}|\cos\alpha \Rightarrow \cos\alpha = \frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}}{|\vec{a}||\vec{b}|}$$

Figure 3: \vec{a}, \vec{b} & \vec{c} are the position vectors of vertices A, B & C of ΔABC in 3D space.

Similarly, it can be found out that

$$\sin\beta = \frac{|\vec{b} \times \vec{c}|}{|\vec{b}||\vec{c}|}, \quad \cos\beta = \frac{\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c}}{|\vec{b}||\vec{c}|}, \quad \sin\gamma = \frac{|\vec{c} \times \vec{a}|}{|\vec{c}||\vec{a}|}, \quad \cos\gamma = \frac{\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a}}{|\vec{c}||\vec{a}|}$$

Now, the solid angle subtended by ΔABC at the origin O is equal to the solid angle subtended by the tetrahedron OABC at the apex O such that α, β & γ are the angles between consecutive lateral edges AO, BO & CO at the vertex O. The solid angle subtended by the tetrahedron is given by above general formula (Eq. (2)) as follows

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\gamma\cos\alpha}{\sin\gamma\sin\alpha}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right)$$

Substituting the values of $\sin\alpha, \cos\alpha, \sin\beta, \cos\beta, \sin\gamma, \cos\gamma$ in the above formula, one should get

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}}{|\vec{a}||\vec{b}|} - \frac{\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c}}{|\vec{b}||\vec{c}|} \cdot \frac{\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a}}{|\vec{c}||\vec{a}|}}{\frac{|\vec{b} \times \vec{c}|}{|\vec{b}||\vec{c}|} \cdot \frac{|\vec{c} \times \vec{a}|}{|\vec{c}||\vec{a}|}}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\frac{\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c}}{|\vec{b}||\vec{c}|} - \frac{\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a}}{|\vec{c}||\vec{a}|} \cdot \frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}}{|\vec{a}||\vec{b}|}}{\frac{|\vec{c} \times \vec{a}|}{|\vec{c}||\vec{a}|} \cdot \frac{|\vec{a} \times \vec{b}|}{|\vec{a}||\vec{b}|}}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\frac{\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a}}{|\vec{c}||\vec{a}|} - \frac{\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b}}{|\vec{a}||\vec{b}|} \cdot \frac{\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c}}{|\vec{b}||\vec{c}|}}{\frac{|\vec{a} \times \vec{b}|}{|\vec{a}||\vec{b}|} \cdot \frac{|\vec{b} \times \vec{c}|}{|\vec{b}||\vec{c}|}}\right)$$

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b})|\vec{c}|^2 - (\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c})(\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a})}{|\vec{b} \times \vec{c}||\vec{c} \times \vec{a}|}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{(\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c})|\vec{a}|^2 - (\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a})(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b})}{|\vec{c} \times \vec{a}||\vec{a} \times \vec{b}|}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{(\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a})|\vec{b}|^2 - (\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b})(\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c})}{|\vec{a} \times \vec{b}||\vec{b} \times \vec{c}|}\right) \dots (3)$$

Above is the general formula to compute the solid angle subtended by any triangle at the origin, given the position vectors of its vertices as \vec{a}, \vec{b} & \vec{c} .

4. Application and validation of formula

Example 1: Compute the solid angle subtended by a tetrahedron at its vertex such that the angles between the consecutive edges meeting at the same vertex are 30° , 40° & 50° .

Sol. In this case, $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 30^\circ + 40^\circ + 50^\circ = 120^\circ < 360^\circ$ (true tetrahedron)

The solid angle ω subtended by a tetrahedron at its vertex is given by general formula (Eq.(2)),

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\gamma\cos\alpha}{\sin\gamma\sin\alpha}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right)$$

Substituting the corresponding values, $\alpha = 30^\circ$, $\beta = 40^\circ$ & $\gamma = 50^\circ$ in the above formula, one should get

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 30^\circ - \cos 40^\circ \cos 50^\circ}{\sin 40^\circ \sin 50^\circ}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 40^\circ - \cos 50^\circ \cos 30^\circ}{\sin 50^\circ \sin 30^\circ}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 50^\circ - \cos 30^\circ \cos 40^\circ}{\sin 30^\circ \sin 40^\circ}\right)$$

$$\omega = 0.709372913 - 0.578342569 - (-0.06422191)$$

$$= 0.773594823 - 0.578342569 = \mathbf{0.195252254 \text{ sr}}$$

Example 2: Compute the solid angle subtended by a tetrahedron at its vertex such that the angles between the consecutive edges meeting at the same vertex are 90° , 90° & 90° .

Sol. In this case, $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 90^\circ + 90^\circ + 90^\circ = 270^\circ < 360^\circ$ (true tetrahedron)

The solid angle ω subtended by a tetrahedron at its vertex is given by general formula (Eq.(2)),

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\gamma\cos\alpha}{\sin\gamma\sin\alpha}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right)$$

Substituting the corresponding values, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 90^\circ$ & $\gamma = 90^\circ$ in the above formula, we get

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 90^\circ - \cos 90^\circ \cos 90^\circ}{\sin 90^\circ \sin 90^\circ}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 90^\circ - \cos 90^\circ \cos 90^\circ}{\sin 90^\circ \sin 90^\circ}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 90^\circ - \cos 90^\circ \cos 90^\circ}{\sin 90^\circ \sin 90^\circ}\right)$$

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}(0) - \sin^{-1}(0) - \sin^{-1}(0) = \frac{\pi}{2} - 0 - 0 = \frac{\pi}{2} \text{ sr}$$

It is obvious that the solid angle subtended by an octant at the origin is $\frac{4\pi}{8} = \frac{\pi}{2}$ sr which is equal to the above value of solid angle subtended by a tetrahedron which is equivalent to an octant. Thus the result is verified.

Example 3: Compute the solid angle subtended by a tetrahedron at its vertex such that the angles between the consecutive edges meeting at the same vertex are 90° , 120° & 150° .

Sol. In this case, $\alpha + \beta + \gamma = 90^\circ + 120^\circ + 150^\circ = 360^\circ \nless 360^\circ$ (not a tetrahedron)

The solid angle ω subtended by a tetrahedron at its vertex is given by general formula (Eq.(2)),

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\alpha - \cos\beta\cos\gamma}{\sin\beta\sin\gamma}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\beta - \cos\gamma\cos\alpha}{\sin\gamma\sin\alpha}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos\gamma - \cos\alpha\cos\beta}{\sin\alpha\sin\beta}\right)$$

Substituting the corresponding values, $\alpha = 90^\circ$, $\beta = 120^\circ$ & $\gamma = 150^\circ$ in the above formula, we get solid angle subtended by a plane at any point on it within its boundary

$$\begin{aligned}\omega &= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 90^\circ - \cos 120^\circ \cos 150^\circ}{\sin 120^\circ \sin 150^\circ}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 120^\circ - \cos 150^\circ \cos 90^\circ}{\sin 150^\circ \sin 90^\circ}\right) \\ &\quad - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{\cos 150^\circ - \cos 90^\circ \cos 120^\circ}{\sin 90^\circ \sin 120^\circ}\right) \\ \omega &= \cos^{-1}(-1) - \sin^{-1}(-1) - \sin^{-1}(-1) \\ &= \pi - \left(-\frac{\pi}{2}\right) - \left(-\frac{\pi}{2}\right) = \pi + \frac{\pi}{2} + \frac{\pi}{2} = 2\pi \text{ sr}\end{aligned}$$

Above result is true for any plane subtending a solid angle of 2π sr at each point on it within its boundary.

Example 4: Compute the solid angle subtended at the origin by a triangle having its vertices at the points $(1, 2, 3)$, $(-2, -3, 1)$ & $(-3, 4, 5)$ in 3D coordinate system.

Sol. In this case, the position vectors of vertices: $\vec{a} = \hat{i} + 2\hat{j} + 3\hat{k}$, $\vec{b} = -2\hat{i} - 3\hat{j} + \hat{k}$ & $\vec{c} = -3\hat{i} + 4\hat{j} + 5\hat{k}$

$$|\vec{a}| = |\hat{i} + 2\hat{j} + 3\hat{k}| = \sqrt{14}, \quad |\vec{b}| = |-2\hat{i} - 3\hat{j} + \hat{k}| = \sqrt{14}, \quad |\vec{c}| = |-3\hat{i} + 4\hat{j} + 5\hat{k}| = 5\sqrt{2}$$

$$\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b} = (\hat{i} + 2\hat{j} + 3\hat{k}) \cdot (-2\hat{i} - 3\hat{j} + \hat{k}) = -5$$

$$\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c} = (-2\hat{i} - 3\hat{j} + \hat{k}) \cdot (-3\hat{i} + 4\hat{j} + 5\hat{k}) = -1$$

$$\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a} = (-3\hat{i} + 4\hat{j} + 5\hat{k}) \cdot (\hat{i} + 2\hat{j} + 3\hat{k}) = 20$$

$$|\vec{a} \times \vec{b}| = |(\hat{i} + 2\hat{j} + 3\hat{k}) \times (-2\hat{i} - 3\hat{j} + \hat{k})| = |11\hat{i} - 7\hat{j} + \hat{k}| = 3\sqrt{19}$$

$$|\vec{b} \times \vec{c}| = |(-2\hat{i} - 3\hat{j} + \hat{k}) \times (-3\hat{i} + 4\hat{j} + 5\hat{k})| = |-19\hat{i} + 7\hat{j} - 17\hat{k}| = \sqrt{699}$$

$$|\vec{c} \times \vec{a}| = |(-3\hat{i} + 4\hat{j} + 5\hat{k}) \times (\hat{i} + 2\hat{j} + 3\hat{k})| = |2\hat{i} + 14\hat{j} - 10\hat{k}| = 10\sqrt{3}$$

The solid angle ω subtended by a triangle at the origin given the position vectors of its vertices is given by Eq.(3),

$$\omega = \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b})|\vec{c}|^2 - (\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c})(\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a})}{|\vec{b} \times \vec{c}||\vec{c} \times \vec{a}|}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{(\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c})|\vec{a}|^2 - (\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a})(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b})}{|\vec{c} \times \vec{a}||\vec{a} \times \vec{b}|}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{(\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a})|\vec{b}|^2 - (\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b})(\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c})}{|\vec{a} \times \vec{b}||\vec{b} \times \vec{c}|}\right)$$

Now, setting all the corresponding values in above Eq.(2), the solid angle subtended by triangle at the origin

$$\begin{aligned}\omega &= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{(-5)(5\sqrt{2})^2 - (-1)(20)}{(\sqrt{699})(10\sqrt{3})}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{(-1)(\sqrt{14})^2 - (20)(-5)}{(10\sqrt{3})(3\sqrt{19})}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{(20)(\sqrt{14})^2 - (-5)(-1)}{(3\sqrt{19})(\sqrt{699})}\right) \\ &= \cos^{-1}\left(\frac{-23}{3\sqrt{233}}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{43}{15\sqrt{57}}\right) - \sin^{-1}\left(\frac{275}{3\sqrt{13281}}\right) \\ &= 2.097006736 - 0.389471206 - 0.919698889 = \mathbf{0.787836641 \text{ sr}}\end{aligned}$$

Example 5: Prove that the solid angle subtended at the origin by any triangle having its vertices at the points $(x, 0, 0)$, $(0, y, 0)$ & $(0, 0, z)$ on the coordinate axes in 3D space is always $\pi/2$ sr. ($\forall x, y, z \in \mathbb{R}$)

Sol. Let the triangle ABC have its vertices at the points $A(x, 0, 0)$, $B(0, y, 0)$ & $C(0, 0, z)$ lying on the coordinate axes x, y & z axes respectively (as shown in Figure 4).

In this case, the position vectors of vertices of ΔABC : $\vec{a} = x\hat{i}$, $\vec{b} = y\hat{j}$ & $\vec{c} = z\hat{k}$

The solid angle ω subtended by a triangle at the origin, given the position vectors of its vertices is given by Eq.(3) as follows

$$\omega = \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b})|\vec{c}|^2 - (\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c})(\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a})}{|\vec{b} \times \vec{c}||\vec{c} \times \vec{a}|} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{(\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c})|\vec{a}|^2 - (\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a})(\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b})}{|\vec{c} \times \vec{a}||\vec{a} \times \vec{b}|} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{(\vec{c} \cdot \vec{a})|\vec{b}|^2 - (\vec{a} \cdot \vec{b})(\vec{b} \cdot \vec{c})}{|\vec{a} \times \vec{b}||\vec{b} \times \vec{c}|} \right)$$

Now, setting the values of all the vectors in the above formula, the solid angle subtended by triangle at the origin

$$\begin{aligned} \omega &= \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{(xi \cdot yj)z^2 - (yj \cdot zk)(zk \cdot xi)}{|yj \times zk||zk \times xi|} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{(yj \cdot zk)x^2 - (zk \cdot xi)(xi \cdot yj)}{|zk \times xi||xi \times yj|} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{(zk \cdot xi)y^2 - (xi \cdot yj)(yj \cdot zk)}{|xi \times yj||yj \times zk|} \right) \\ &= \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{xyz^2(i \cdot j) - xyz^2(j \cdot k)(k \cdot i)}{xyz^2|j \times k||k \times i|} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{x^2yz(j \cdot k) - x^2yz(k \cdot i)(i \cdot j)}{x^2yz|k \times i||i \times j|} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{xy^2z(k \cdot i) - xy^2z(i \cdot j)(j \cdot k)}{xy^2z|i \times j||j \times k|} \right) \\ &= \cos^{-1} \left(\frac{(i \cdot j) - (j \cdot k)(k \cdot i)}{|j \times k||k \times i|} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{(j \cdot k) - (k \cdot i)(i \cdot j)}{|k \times i||i \times j|} \right) - \sin^{-1} \left(\frac{(k \cdot i) - (i \cdot j)(j \cdot k)}{|i \times j||j \times k|} \right) \\ &= \cos^{-1}(0) - \sin^{-1}(0) - \sin^{-1}(0) = \frac{\pi}{2} - 0 - 0 = \frac{\pi}{2} \text{ sr} \end{aligned}$$

It is obvious that the **solid angle subtended at the origin by any triangle having its vertices on three coordinate axes is always $\pi/2$ sr**. It also shows that the solid angle subtended by an octant at the origin is $\frac{4\pi}{8} = \frac{\pi}{2}$ sr which is equal to the above value of solid angle subtended at the origin by a triangle with vertices on the coordinate axes, which is equivalent to an octant. Thus the result is proved & verified.

Conclusions: It can be concluded that the derived general formula yields exact values of the solid angle subtended by an arbitrary tetrahedron at a vertex when the angles between consecutive lateral edges meeting at that vertex are known, as the formulation involves no approximations. The same analytical framework also provides a precise method for computing the solid angle subtended by a triangle at the origin, given the position vectors of its three vertices in a three-dimensional coordinate system. Owing to its exact and general nature, the proposed formula is applicable to a wide range of geometric configurations.

Note: Above articles had been derived & illustrated by Mr H.C. Rajpoot (B Tech, Mechanical Engineering)

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Figure 4: $A(x, 0, 0)$, $B(0, y, 0)$ & $C(0, 0, z)$ are the vertices of ΔABC lying on the coordinate axes x, y, & z respectively.

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